

Sample-Efficient Blockage Prediction and Handover Using Causal Reinforcement Learning

Tamizharasan Kanagamani, Jishnu Sadasivan, Serene Banerjee
Ericsson Research, Bangalore, India

tamizharasan.mit@gmail.com , {jishnu.sadasivan, serene.banerjee}@ericsson.com

Abstract— Blockage prediction and handover are crucial for network controllers to ensure seamless communication and provide uninterrupted user services. Prior knowledge of blockage allows the serving base station to proactively handover the user equipment to the best available base stations. Traditional approaches for blockage prediction have relied on heuristics and statistical analysis, which cannot often capture the complex and dynamic nature of the network and the environmental conditions. Therefore, there is a need for advanced data-driven techniques that adaptively learn the evolving nature of blockages and effectively predict them before they occur. Hence, we propose reinforcement learning (RL) based approaches for blockage prediction and handover. First, we consider popular RL approaches (Deep Q Network and Actor-Critic) to verify the feasibility in the blockage prediction and handover problem. Next, we propose blockage prediction using the Causal RL framework for discrete and continuous action settings. The proposed Causal RL approaches perform better than their conventional RL counterparts in terms of sample efficiency, blockage prediction and handover. Here, the Causal RL in discrete action space achieves an accuracy of 99% in blockage prediction and handover.

Keywords—Blockage prediction, handover, Causal Reinforcement Learning, DeepMIMO,

I. INTRODUCTION

The onset of 6G networks promises revolutionary-high-speed connectivity, low latency, and support for many devices. However, deploying 6G networks poses significant challenges due to increased network complexity, congestion, and various obstacles that can cause blockages [1-4]. A blockage occurs when the signal propagation between a base station (BS) and user equipment (UE) is interrupted, reducing network performance and potential service disruptions. The sensitivity of millimeter waves to blockages is a fundamental challenge. A sudden blockage in the line-of-sight (LOS) path between the BS and devices leads to disconnection, severely impacting reliability. Reconnecting to a new BS incurs high-beam training overhead and introduces critical latency issues.

Existing technology for blockage prediction in 6G faces several challenges and limitations. 6G networks are highly dynamic, with the movement of objects in the environment, changes in the position of UE, changing network conditions, and environmental factors. Existing algorithms often struggle to adapt to these dynamic changes effectively. Static approaches that do not account for temporal and spatial variations in the network and environment conditions may fail to capture the evolving nature of blockages. As a result, the predictions generated may be outdated and less accurate [5].

On the other hand, traditional blockage prediction approaches are often reactive, meaning they identify blockages after they have occurred or when the network performance has already degraded [2]. This reactive nature limits the ability to take proactive measures. Network operators cannot adjust transmission parameters or reroute traffic in advance without timely predictions to ensure uninterrupted connectivity. Thus, proactive management is essential to improve network reliability and user experience.

Alkateeb et al. [4] proposed a supervised learning approach to predict the blockage/handover status. A gated recurrent network takes beam vectors as input and predicts the blockage and handover status at the next time step. Note that different sites have different objects, and their positions and movements vary across sites. Therefore, a model trained on one site will not perform well on other (new) sites. Training models require high-quality, site-specific labeled data. Collecting this high-quality labeled data for different sites is difficult in practice. To overcome these difficulties, viable machine learning (ML) techniques that adapt to the environment's dynamic nature, possess good learning efficiency, and generalize well to different sites are needed.

We need to explore the causal relations to overcome these limitations and provide more accurate and proactive blockage predictions. Causal relationships between network conditions and traffic data are crucial in accurately predicting blockages. Without a causal understanding, it becomes challenging to differentiate between spurious correlations and genuine cause-effect relationships, leading to unreliable predictions. However, the existing blockage prediction and approaches do not utilize causal discovery to improve the performance.

In this study, in contrast to the supervised ML techniques, we propose blockage prediction using a causal Reinforcement learning (RL) approach. RL methods do not necessitate expensive labeled data and are renowned for their capacity to adapt to dynamic environmental conditions [5]. First, we have modeled blockage prediction using conventional RL approaches (Deep Q network (DQN) and Actor-Critic (AC) network). Then, to improve the learning efficiency and performance, we have proposed Causal RL approaches. In the Causal RL framework, we have considered two cases: the discrete action space and the continuous action space. To exhibit the effectiveness of the proposed formulation, we have considered the DeepMIMO (dynamic outdoor O2 scenario) dataset [6]. It is observed that the proposed causal RL framework shows better performance compared to the conventional RL technique in terms of sample efficiency.

The paper organization is as follows. Section II discusses our proposed methods and results. Section III elaborates the results, and Section IV concludes the paper.

II. METHOD AND RESULTS

We devise the blockage prediction and handover as an RL problem, where the goal is to predict a blockage before it occurs and hand it over to the best base station. Here, the best base station provides better channel quality with the UE than other base stations. The channel state information (CSI) values indicate the channel quality. If a complete blockage occurs, the CSI values become zero. Therefore, in the handover problem, the goal is to identify the BS with the best CSI values for handover. This allows the serving base station to proactively handover to the next best base station.

A. RL Environment using DeepMIMO data

To illustrate the effectiveness of RL applications in blockage prediction and handover, we have used the DeepMIMO dataset (designed for ML research in mmWave and MIMO applications) [6]. The DeepMIMO framework can simulate the vehicles, the BS, and the UE information to estimate the CSI matrix. It uses a 3D ray-tracing simulator to generate a dataset comprising mmWave and sub-6GHz channels in the dynamic outdoor O2 Scenario. The O2 Scenario contains three streets and two intersections. A horizontal street is the main street where vehicles move in four lanes (two lanes in each direction). These moving vehicles act as reflecting surfaces and blockages in the network environment. The dataset contains 1000 scenes, which are continuously sampled with a sampling time of 100 ms. At each scene, the corresponding locations of the vehicles are available. This scenario comprises two base stations (BS1 and BS2) and ~116000 users. The CSI matrix and blockage information between users and base stations are also available for each scene. The dataset can be generated with two operating frequencies, 3.4 GHz and 3.5 GHz. In the base stations, the antenna array element is an isotropic antenna.

More specifically, this work utilizes traffic data that contains vehicle location and velocity and employs Causal RL techniques to predict blockages in 6G networks. The DeepMIMO O2 scenario dataset details the user location, BS location, vehicle location, vehicle velocity, and the CSI matrix. Here, the CSI values denote the connectivity between the user and the BS. Non-zero CSI value means there is connectivity between the user and the BS. If the CSI value is zero, then there is no connectivity between the user and the BS, which denotes blockage. The UE will generally be connected to a particular BS. As the vehicles on the road move, it might cause a blockage between the user and the BS. The objective of the study is to identify the blockages between the user and the BS caused by vehicle crossing. Once the blockage is predicted before it happens, the connectivity can be safely handed over to a better BS. We show the performance improvement of the proposed Causal RL techniques over the conventional RL in terms of learning efficiency. By leveraging the publicly available DeepMIMO dataset [6], the proposed method enables network controllers to proactively identify potential blockages and take appropriate measures to optimize network performance and

ensure uninterrupted connectivity. The proposed approach provides a valuable tool for improving the reliability and efficiency of 6G networks. The key elements used in any RL problem are state, action, and reward. In this DeepMIMO environment, the components of each element are as follows. The state information comprises UE location, vehicle location, speed, and BS location. The action denotes the selection of one among the available base stations (BS1 and BS2). The reward consists of the sum of the absolute value of the CSI matrix element, blockage Information (0- blockage, non-zero – no blockage), and the switching information. Switching information denotes if the agent is choosing the same base station or a different base station as compared to the previously selected base station. This is used to avoid unnecessary switches between base stations.

B. Blockage prediction and handover

We consider two conventional methods for blockage prediction: The deep Q and the Actor-Critic network [7].

C. Deep Q-Network (DQN)

DQN is a popular model-free RL algorithm that combines Q-learning with a deep neural network (DNN). DQN overcomes the limitations of the traditional Q-learning algorithm by utilizing a deep neural network as a function approximator to estimate the Q-values. This enables DQN to handle high-dimensional state spaces. The architecture of a DQN consists of a deep neural network that uses the current state as input and outputs Q-values for each possible action.

a. Network Architecture

We have used multimodal Deep Q-Network (MDQN), an extension of DQN that incorporates multiple input data modalities to enhance learning and decision-making. In the proposed work, the network takes input as three modalities: the location of UE and vehicles with dimension 103, the velocity of dimension 103, and the channel state information of dimension 32. The second layer in the network for each modality contains 64, 64, and 16 neurons, respectively. Similarly, the third layer includes 32, 32, and 8 neurons. The output at the third layer is concatenated to form a single vector of dimension 72, which is further connected to the next layer with 32 neurons. The output layer has two neurons that predict the Q values corresponding to each BS selection action.

D. Actor-Critic

Actor-critic is a model-free RL algorithm that combines the strengths of both policy-based and value-based methods [7]. It consists of two modules: an actor and a critic. The actor decides actions based on the current policy, while the critic evaluates the value of the selected actions. The actor and the critic are typically implemented as DNN, where the actor receives the current state as input and estimates the probability distribution over the action space. The critic estimates the value for the action the actor selects for the current state.

Like the DQN, the Actor-Critic Network also receives the multimodal input (location, velocity, and CSI). The Actor network uses the same architecture until the features of the three modal inputs are combined, as described in the DQN network. From the concatenated features, the actor produces a

probabilistic output with two dimensions (representing actions) through a hidden layer of dimension 16. Similarly, the critic network also receives the multimodal input along with the action chosen by the actor. From the concatenated features, the critic estimates the value from a single neuron via a hidden layer of dimension 16. In the actor and critic networks, all the layers use the Leaky-ReLU activation function, except that the output layer of the actor uses the softmax function, and the critic uses no activation function at the output layer.

Figure 1 Evaluation of Cumulative reward (a) and correct BS selection (b).

E. Training

The training procedure for DQN involves iteratively updating the network parameters to minimize the Temporal Difference error (TD), which is the difference between the current Q-value estimation and the target Q-value. Experience Replay and Target Network techniques are employed to stabilize the learning process and mitigate the issues of sample correlation and target instability. For the Actor-Critic Network, the training procedure involves updating the actor's policy using policy gradients and updating the critic's value function using temporal difference learning.

The DeepMIMO environment is used to generate the data for 1000 random users from the three user grids. Each episode comprises a step length of 30, where each step represents the continuous scenes. For each step, the state information comprises the vehicle location, vehicle speed, UE location, and BS locations. Here, the action refers to the selection of a base station (BS1 or BS2) for handover. The reward comprises three components: CSI, Blockage information (BI), and switching information (SI). The CSI value represents the strength of the received signal in the UE. Blockage information (BI) denotes whether the path between the user and the selected BS is blocked or not, $BI = 0$ represents a blockage between the user and the BS, and $BI = 1$ represents the availability of connection between them. Switching information denotes if the agent is choosing the same BS or a different BS as compared to the previously selected BS. We assume that vehicle velocity and positions are estimated using sensing algorithms in a real-world scenario.

Figure 1(a) shows the performance comparison between DQN and Actor-Critic in terms of reward, and Figure 1(b) shows the number of times the agent selects the best action. It is observed that for both the RL algorithms, the cumulative reward increases as we train. The Actor-Critic method shows a higher performance than the DQN. After converging, It can predict correct actions with an accuracy of 97%. Figure 2 shows actions the Actor-Critic method took on example

episodes. The first row shows the actual active/blocking conditions for each base station at each step in two episodes. The second row shows the base station selection by model at each time step in the respective episodes. It is observed that the conventional RL framework can predict blockages and handover effectively.

Figure 2 Actions selected for two episodes where the first and second row shows blocking conditions, actions selected for each episode, respectively.

F. Causal RL in Discrete Action Space

We have proposed a Causal RL-based algorithm for blockage prediction and handover in the discrete action space as in the DQN and Actor-critic methods. The Causal RL framework helps to optimize the time required to learn the policy and environment. It is particularly useful in a scenario where the dimension of the action space is huge. For example, if the number of base stations present is large, the conventional RL approaches consider exploration assuming all the BSs are equally relevant (c.f. Figure 3) and do not exploit the nature of the actual environment (for a specific UE, only a few BSs might be relevant (c.f. Figure 4)). On the other hand, the Causal RL framework learns the relevant BS information faster and reduces the exploration overhead. The proposed approach achieves efficient learning by introducing causality to the RL problem. Here, in the given action space, it chooses the reliable/necessary (causally related) actions more often than others for exploration and exploitation. We introduce causality in an actor-critic-based approach using a Selector network (c.f. Figure 5).

Figure 3: Conventional RL giving importance for all the actions.

Figure 4: Causal RL gives importance on relevant actions.

Here, the actor-critic network uses the same architecture described in the earlier case. The proposed Selector network uses the same architecture as the Actor network, except that the output layer uses the sigmoid activation function to estimate the confidence in the actions.

Figure 5 Actor-critic with selector network.

In the proposed Causal RL approach, a selector network gives confidence in the action chosen by the actor-critic network. A pseudo-code of the proposed framework is given in **Algorithm 1**. The actor-critic network tries to optimize the performance to maximize the cumulative reward by opting for the best action by the actor. The selector network allows us to minimize the time required to reach the best performance. It does it by acting as a confidence provider. For a given state, the selector network provides the confidence with value in terms of probability for each action. If the action chosen by the actor has high confidence according to the selector, then the action is chosen (exploitation). Exploration occurs if the selector gives low confidence for that particular action. This way, when the action provided by the actor and the selector networks match, exploitation takes place; exploration happens otherwise. This confidence-based exploration-exploitation helps attain the best performance in a relatively shorter duration. An alternate view is that the selector intervenes in actions suggested by the actor to uncover the causal relations between state, action, and reward.

If domain knowledge is available, one can further incorporate this information to enhance learning efficiency. For example, suppose we know from expert knowledge that certain actions are causally related to the reward for a particular state. In that case, one can incorporate this information by assigning a probability value '1' to the selector network output corresponding to that particular action.

Algorithm 1: Selector Controlled Actor-Critic

Initialize critic network C_{ϕ} , policy network π_v , and selector network G_{θ} .

Initialize target critic networks. $C_{\phi'}$, and target policy network $\pi_{v'}$.

For $t \rightarrow 1$ to N do

Interact with the environment using the given policy and store transition tuple (s, a, r, s') in the replay buffer B .

```
{
     $a_{\pi} = \text{softmax}(\pi_{\theta})$ 
     $a_G = \{i \mid G_{\theta}(i) > \lambda\}$  where  $\lambda$  is threshold
    if  $a_{\pi} \subset a_G$  use  $a_{\pi}$ 
    Else, choose a random action
}
```

Sample mini-batch transition (s, a, r, s') from B .

$$a'_{\pi} = \text{argmax}_a(\pi_{v'}(s'))$$

$$a'_G = \text{argmax}_a(G_{\theta'}(s'))$$

Calculate target critic value y_c :

$$y_c = r + \gamma \max[C_{\phi'}(s', a'_{\pi}), C_{\phi'}(s', a'_G)]$$

Update critic:

$$\Phi_i = \text{argmin}_{\Phi_i} \text{MSE}(y_c, C_{\Phi_i}(s, a))$$

Update selector network G_{θ} :

$$H = -\sum_i a_{\pi_i} \log(a_G)$$

$$\theta = \begin{cases} \theta - \Delta H & \text{if } C_{\Phi_i}(s, a_{\pi}) > C_{\Phi_i}(s, a_G) \\ \text{No Update} & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

Update v by the deterministic policy gradient, with the learning rate η_2

$$v = v - \eta_2 \Delta_a C_{\Phi_i}(s, a)_{a=\pi_v(s)} \Delta \pi_v(s)$$

The performance of the proposed selector-controlled Actor-Critic is compared with the conventional Actor-Critic, where the settings considered are the same as those of the conventional RL-based blockage prediction methods.

Figure 6 Cumulative reward (a) and percentage of correct actions selected (b), comparison between Actor-Critic and with Selector.

It is observed that when combined with the Actor-Critic network, the selector learns the environment relatively faster than training with the Actor-Critic network alone. It achieves better performance by estimating the confidence value for each action. As the exploitation takes place after confirming an action from two different networks, initially, it performs more exploration, and over time, the proposed model starts exploiting more on the states with better confidence.

Figure 6 compares the performance of the proposed selector-controlled actor-critic (Causal RL) method with that of the conventional actor-critic method (a) average cumulative reward and (b) percentage of correct actions selected. It can be viewed that the proposed approach shows higher performance in terms of better average cumulative reward and the selection of best actions. The proposed framework is also sample-efficient and learns faster (requiring fewer episodes to learn). The proposed Causal RL framework reached convergence in approximately 150 episodes.

G. Causal RL framework for Continuous Action Space

Regarding Causal RL on continuous action space, we propose to use TD3-INVASE [7] for blockage prediction and handover. In TD3-INVASE, causal discovery is addressed as a state-wise action selection problem where interventions are applied on the primary action space to estimate the causal link between the action space and reward. The agent explores its environment by taking actions and observing the resulting states, rewards, and next states. It stores these experiences as tuples (s, a, r, s') in a replay buffer. States and actions are randomly sampled from the replay buffer and given as input to a selector network. The selector network computes the selection probabilities, indicating the importance of each dimension in the action space. A selection mask is generated according to the selection probability vector. By multiplying this "selection mask" by the action vector, the agent selects the most relevant action components for achieving the desired reward. This selective approach (essentially an intervention) allows the agent to uncover the causal relationships between the specific action dimension and reward. Even though causal relations can be learned from data, domain knowledge can be incorporated through selection mask probabilities. Specifically, one can set the mask value to one for causally related actions and zero for unrelated actions. The critic network minimizes the Temporal Difference (TD) error based on the state and selected action dimensions. In contrast, the baseline network minimizes the TD error based on the states and the original action space. The difference between these TD errors is used to compute the policy gradient, which updates the selector network.

Since the action space considered in TD3-INVASE is continuous, we need to devise actions (corresponding to the BS selection) in a continuous space. Here, we consider the reward as the sum of the absolute value of the channel matrix obtained after taking the action and state consisting of locations of UE and BSs, vehicle locations, velocity of vehicles, and the BS-UE current channel matrix. The action space is devised to be continuous as follows. Let \mathbf{a} be the action, which is a vector of dimension d , where a_i denotes the i th dimension of the action and $a_i \in [-2, 2]$ for $1 \leq i \leq d$. The dimension of the action space we considered is 101, ($d = 101$) where the first component of the action (a_1) is the only dimension of action space that selects the BSs, and all other action dimensions are irrelevant (not causally related to the reward). To select the BSs, based on the first component of the action, we consider the following rule: select base station 1 when a_1 has a positive value and select the base station 2 otherwise. The causally unrelated action dimensions (a_i where $2 \leq i \leq d$) does not affect the reward (or

environment). If more than two base stations are available in the network, we can select the relevant BSs by considering a relevant rule on the action component. For example, if $a_m > 0$, then select the m^{th} base station.

We compare the blockage prediction and handover performance of TD3-INVASE with the Twin Delayed Deep Deterministic policy gradient algorithm (TD3). We used the same model parameter setting as in TD3 and TD3-INVASE [7]. We collect data for 1000 episodes initially, and training starts after 1000 episodes, where each episode has a length of 30 steps. Figure 7 shows the reward plot during training. It is

Figure 7 Reward comparison between TD3 and TD3-INVASE.

observed that both TD3 and TD3-INVASE improve the rewards. The reward fluctuation is primarily attributed to the fact that each step exploration noise is added to the action.

Figure 8 Performance comparison between TD3 and TD3-Invase in terms of average reward (a) and percentage of correct actions taken (b).

Performance comparison of TD3-INVASE with TD3 is shown in Figure 8, where each evaluation is performed after every 500 training steps. For each evaluation, 100 episodes are considered, where (a) shows the evaluation of performance in terms of average reward and (b) shows the percentage of correct actions taken. From Figure 8, it is observed that both TD3 and TD3-INVASE can improve the rewards. Compared to TD3, TD3-INVASE shows a superior performance in terms of average cumulative reward. The higher reward of TD3-INVASE compared to TD3 indicates that the TD3-INVASE is sample efficient, and it achieves a performance of $\sim 80\%$ in predicting correct actions.

III. DISCUSSION

In this work, we first demonstrate RL algorithms for blockage prediction and handover problems. Then, to improve the performance, we have used Causal RL. This work shows that the Causal RL approach efficiently explores the action space. The Causal RL framework intervenes in the action space and selects the causally relevant actions. This increases the exploration on the relevant action space and reduces the exploration in the irrelevant action space, enabling sample-

efficient learning for blockage prediction and handover. We consider both discrete and continuous action space scenarios for blockage prediction and handover to show that the proposed Causal RL formulation outperforms the traditional RL algorithms in both cases.

The proposed RL-based blockage prediction system gives an edge over other approaches in various ways. For a dynamic environment, the conventional blockage prediction algorithms often struggle to account for the evolving nature of the blockages, and the predictions become less accurate, hence necessitating RL-based approaches. The proposed blockage prediction algorithms that are based on the RL approach can easily adapt to changes in the environment and maintain prediction performance even in dynamic environments. Unlike the conventional blockage prediction and handover algorithms based on supervised learning, the proposed RL-based framework does not require any labeled data. Since no labeled data is needed, developing RL-based algorithms is easy, cost-effective, and can be used effectively in new sites.

The proposed Causal RL framework uses a selector network along with the conventional Actor-Critic network for the discrete action space. The actor-critic network tries to maximize the cumulative reward by choosing the best action. Using the selector network allows us to minimize the time required to reach the best performance. It does it by acting as a confidence provider. For a given state, the selector network estimates the confidence value for each action in terms of probability. Similarly, the actor also chooses an action for the given state. If the action chosen by the actor has high confidence according to the selector, then the action is chosen (exploitation). Exploration occurs if the selector gives low confidence for that particular action. This way, when the action provided by the actor and the selector networks match, exploitation takes place; exploration happens otherwise. This confidence-based exploration-exploitation helps attain the best performance in a relatively shorter duration. The other advantage is that we can easily extend to the case where the number of BS is more. Similarly, we can add the selection of antenna angles in addition to the BS selection, where the action should select the antenna angle (from a quantized set of antenna angles) and BS to improve the CSI values.

For the continuous action space scenario, we have used the instance-wise variable selection in the temporal difference learning framework (TD3-INVASE) presented in [7] to conduct interventions on the action space during training to discover the causal relationship between the action space and the reward. This TD3-INVASE-based Causal RL framework helps to incorporate any continuous actions for blockage prediction and handover. For example, antenna rotation selection and BS selection can be considered where the rotation angle can be continuous, and a certain antenna rotation may not be causally relevant.

The proposed Causal RL framework can discover the causal relation between the states, actions, and rewards, improving efficient exploration and exploitation. This facilitates the sample efficient learning compared to the conventional RL-based handover/blockage prediction. In the proposed approach, a data-driven approach is used to discover

the causal relations; however, the proposed approach can incorporate the expert/domain knowledge in the framework for efficiently discovering/utilizing the causal relations.

The proposed methods allow proactive management of network resources by taking appropriate actions to mitigate blockages. This improves network performance and user experience, and ensures uninterrupted connectivity. This also improves network reliability, and reduces downtime. Although the proposed methods can anticipate blockages in familiar settings, they frequently have trouble adapting to novel settings. These methods need to be improved to obtain greater generalization capabilities for use in practical situations. This enhancement to the model involves the mechanisms that allow the models to learn and derive more resilient, transferable causal representations. Incorporating causal representation learning into these models can improve their generalization capability.

IV. CONCLUSION

We have demonstrated the feasibility of using the RL framework for blockage prediction and handover with DeepMIMO. We have shown that the Causal RL is more sample-efficient than conventional RL. It is observed that irrespective of whether the actions are in the continuous domain or discrete domain, the causal RL framework shows superior performance in terms of sample efficiency and cumulative reward. Also, for the given environmental settings on blockage prediction and handover problem, the proposed discrete domain Causal RL framework performs better than all other algorithms and achieves a performance accuracy of ~99% in the correct action prediction. The proposed framework is easily extendable to the scenario where one considers the rotation of antennas in the BS also.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work has been partly funded by the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation program and Smart Networks and Services Joint Undertaking (SNS JU) under grant agreement no: 101096034 (VERGE Project).

REFERENCES

- [1] Mahamod, U., Mohamad, H., Shayea, I., Othman, M. and Asuhaimi, F.A., "Handover parameter for self-optimisation in 6G mobile networks: A survey". *Alexandria Eng. Journal*, 78, pp.104-119, 2023.
- [2] Charan, G., Muhammad A., and Ahmed Alkhateeb. "Vision-aided 6G wireless communications: Blockage prediction and proactive handoff." *IEEE Trans. on Vehicular Tech.* 70, no. 10 (2021): 10193-10208.
- [3] Vankayala, S.K., Gollapudi, S.K.S., Singh, S., Jain, B., Yoon, S. and Bashir, A.K., "Deep-learning based proactive handover for 5G/6G mobile networks using wireless information", In *Proc. IEEE Int. Conf. on Global Comm. (Globecom)*, Dec. 2022, pp. 461-466.
- [4] A. Alkhateeb, I. Beltagy and S. Alex, "Machine learning for reliable MMWAVE systems: blockage prediction and proactive handoff", *IEEE Global Conf. on Signal and Information Proc. (GlobalSIP)*, 2018.
- [5] Padakandla, S. "A survey of reinforcement learning algorithms for dynamically varying environments." *ACM Computing*, 54.6, 2021.
- [6] A. Alkhateeb, "DeepMIMO: A Generic Deep Learning Dataset for Millimeter Wave and Massive MIMO Applications", *Proc. of Information Theory and Applications workshop*, CA, 2019, pp. 1-8
- [7] H. Sun and T. Wang, "Toward Causal-Aware RL: State-Wise Action-Refined Temporal Difference", *Deep RL Workshop at 36th Conference on Neural Information Processing Systems 2022*.